

Solvent Effects on Electronic Spectra of Some Amino Salts of d-Camphor- β -Sulphonic Acid

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The electronic spectra of amino salts of d-camphor- β -sulphonic acid were examined in a series of solvents covering a wide range of polarity. The transition energies (E_T) were plotted against Z-values, a solvent polarity parameter. A linear relationship was observed between transition energy and Z-value for the $\sigma \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. Solvent sensitivities of the amino salts have also been calculated and found to be in the increasing order as the inductive nature of the side chain increases, with the anomaly in ammonium salt. The anomaly in ammonium salt has been explained in terms of hydrogen bonding.

CAMPHOR- β -sulphonic acid is a strong monobasic acid and its salts generally do not undergo hydrolysis. The ketonic group is common to all the amino derivative of d-camphor- β -sulphonic acid. The low intensity uv absorption of saturated keto compounds has been undeservedly ignored by many organic chemists. The only complete study of the simple keto compounds is that of Maroni¹, who measured the uv maxima of 32 alkyl ketones in three solvents, hexane, ethanol and water. Ignorance of appreciable solvent effect on many electronic transitions has often led to the failure to mention the solvent used in the uv measurement. Solvents often have a considerable effect on the uv spectra of organic compounds. These solvent effects are useful in determining the electronic transition and to find out different types of solute-solvent interactions*. Kosower² has developed a solvent polarity parameter, Z, which has been used successfully in correlating a number of solvent effects on $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the effect of solvents of varying polarity on the electronic transition of amino salts of d-camphor- β -sulphonic acid. An attempt has been made to analyse the results in terms of solvent polarity parameter Z. It is observed that Z-values are useful in the analysis of the results.

Experimental

Chemicals - Compounds were prepared as described by Pant⁴. All the solvents used were of either B.D.H., AnalaR or E.M., G.R. quality. Freshly distilled⁵ solvents were used in all the experiments.

Spectra The absorption spectra were recorded using very dilute solutions of the compounds at $26 \pm 1^\circ$, on a Hitachi Perkin-Elmer 139 UV-VIS spectrophotometer. The molecular extinction coefficients, ϵ , were calculated from the observed values of absorption at different wavelengths.

The oscillator strength, 'f' was calculated from the following relation: $f = 4.32 \times 10^{-9} \int \epsilon dv$, utilising $\epsilon_{\max} = \int \epsilon dv$,

where $\Delta \bar{\nu}$ is the half bandwidth in wave numbers. The transition energy, E_T was calculated from the relation

$$E_T (\text{kcal mol}^{-1}) = \frac{2.859 \times 10^6}{\lambda_{\max} \times (\text{\AA})}$$

The spectra methylamine, ethylamine, ethanamine, dimethylamine, isopropylamine and n-propylamine salts of d-camphor- β -sulphonic acid were measured in a series of solvents, varying in polarity from chloroform (Z, 63.2) to water (Z, 94.6). The results are summarized in Tables 1-4. The transition energies in different solvents are plotted against Z-values (Figs. 1-7).

Results and Discussion

It is well known that simple aliphatic aldehydes and ketones usually exhibit a weak absorption band with fine structure in the range 230-350 nm and have maximum absorption in the region 280-300 nm ($\epsilon_{\max} \approx 10$, $f \approx 10^{-4}$). This band is attributed to the one electron singlet-singlet transition from non-bonding p-orbital to the antibonding π -orbital, namely the (s-s) $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. This transition in carbonyl compounds is forbidden⁶. It is evident from the results (Tables 1-4), that all the amino-derivatives of d-camphor- β -sulphonic acid exhibit weak absorption maximum in the range 285-290 nm. The band has been assigned to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ carbonyl transition, on the basis of the following criteria: (i) low band intensity, (ii) blue shift of the band with increasing solvent polarity and (iii) obliteration of vibrational fine structure on changing from non-polar to polar media⁷.

Fig. 1. Ammonium salt of d-camphor- β -sulphonate.

Fig. 3. Ethylamino-d-camphor- β -sulphonate.

Fig. 2. Methylamino-d-camphor- β -sulphonate.

Fig. 4. Dimethylamino-d-camphor- β -sulphonate.

Fig. 5. n-Propylamino-d-camphor- β -sulphonate.

Fig. 7. Ethanolamino-d-camphor- β -sulphonate.

Fig. 6. Isopropylamino-d-camphor- β -sulphonate.

TABLE I—SPECTRAL DATA ON AMMONIUM SALT OF d-CAMPHOR- β -SULPHONIC ACID

Sl. no.	Solvent	Z	Dielectric constant	λ_{max}	ϵ_{max}	E_T kcal mol ⁻¹	f
1.	Dioxane*	—	2.21	—	—	—	—
2.	Chloroform* (CF)	68.2	5.06	—	—	—	—
3.	Dichloro-methane (DM)	64.2	9.04	—	—	—	—
4.	Pyridine (Py)	64.0	12.30	290	34.38	98.58	—
5.	Isopropanol (i-PrOH)	76.3	18.30	290	25.00	98.58	1.080
6.	Ethanol (EtOH)	79.6	24.80	288	35.00	99.27	2.420
7.	Methanol (MeOH)	83.6	32.60	287	31.25	99.62	1.360
8.	Acetonitrile* (An)	71.3	36.20	—	—	—	—
9.	Dimethyl formamide (DMF)	68.5	37.00	289	31.00	98.93	1.311
10.	Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO)	71.1	46.60	289	31.25	98.93	1.431
11.	Water (H ₂ O)	94.6	80.00	285	40.62	100.32	3.760

* Ammonium salt of d-camphor- β -sulphonic acid not soluble.

Examination of these results shows that on changing the solvent from chloroform to water, the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition band exhibits a small blue shift. The $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions observed in different solvents are very

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL DATA ON d-CAMPHOR-β-SULPHONIC ACID SALTS

Solvent*	Methylamine salt				Dimethylamine salt			
	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{max}	ET kcal mol ⁻¹	f × 10 ⁴	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{max}	ET kcal mol ⁻¹	f × 10 ⁴
Dioxane	290.0	19.975	98.58	0.569	290.0	21.50	98.58	0.750
CF	290.1	87.000	98.58	2.877	291.0	85.00	98.25	2.827
DM	291.0	38.750	98.34	2.223	292.0	53.18	97.91	5.586
Py	—	—	—	—	297.0	1268.9	96.26	—
i-PrOH	288.0	23.125	99.27	0.850	289.0	26.88	98.93	1.168
EtOH	287.5	28.125	99.47	1.242	287.5	88.75	99.27	3.645
					286.0	30.00		
MeOH	287.0	38.75	99.62	2.412	287.0	36.25	99.62	2.528
An	289.5	25.00	98.75	0.918	289.0	26.26	98.93	1.043
DMF	288.5	19.00	99.10	0.899	289.0	32.62	99.93	1.254
DMSO	289.0	19.00	98.93	0.426	287.5	16.95	99.62	0.945
H ₂ O	285.0	39.77	100.82	0.157	285.0	45.00	100.32	4.868

* Abbreviation as in Table 1.

TABLE 3—SPECTRAL DATA ON d-CAMPHOR-β-SULPHONIC ACID SALTS

Solvent*	Ethylamine salt				n-Propylamine salt			
	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{max}	ET kcal mol ⁻¹	f × 10 ⁴	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{max}	ET kcal mol ⁻¹	f × 10 ⁴
Dioxane	290.0	21.125	98.52	0.643	290.0	26.250	98.58	1.010
CF	290.0	80.000	98.58	1.872	290.0	87.500	98.58	3.018
DM	290.0	87.500	98.58	1.247	290.0	87.500	98.58	2.897
Py	297.0	1268.75	96.28	—	—	—	—	—
i-PrOH	288.0	21.250	99.27	0.698	288.0	25.500	99.27	1.432
EtOH	287.0	21.250	99.62	1.998	288.0	36.250	99.27	2.939
MeOH	286.0	42.500	99.96	4.378	287.0	35.500	99.62	3.659
An	289.5	25.000	98.76	0.907	289.5	26.687	97.76	1.145
DMF	289.0	31.000	98.93	1.473	288.5	25.070	99.10	0.888
DMSO	288.0	18.000	99.27	0.406	288.5	29.317	99.10	1.211
H ₂ O	285.0	47.500	100.32	5.270	285.0	37.500	100.32	3.175

* Abbreviation as in Table 1.

TABLE 4—SPECTRAL DATA ON d-CAMPHOR-β-SULPHONIC ACID SALTS

Solvent*	Isopropylamine salt				Ethanolamine salt			
	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{max}	ET kcal mol ⁻¹	f × 10 ⁴	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{max}	ET kcal mol ⁻¹	f × 10 ⁴
Dioxane	290.0	20.000	98.58	0.674	290.0	21.250	98.58	0.778
CF	291.0	86.750	98.25	2.880	290.5	43.750	98.42	4.287
DM	292.0	58.970	97.91	7.812	290.0	35.000	98.58	3.736
Py	297.0	1268.12	96.26	—	—	—	—	—
i-PrOH	288.0	28.375	99.27	1.435	288.0	23.770	99.27	0.854
EtOH	287.0	41.875	99.62	3.918	288.0	43.770	99.27	4.285
MeOH	286.0	45.000	99.96	5.053	287.0	47.000	99.02	5.813
An	289.5	25.000	98.76	0.918	289.5	29.120	98.76	1.446
DMF	288.5	31.000	99.10	1.073	289.0	29.120	98.93	0.939
DMSO	288.5	26.250	99.10	1.089	288.0	18.750	99.27	0.854
H ₂ O	285.0	46.250	100.32	5.140	285.0	43.750	100.32	4.205

* Abbreviation as in Table 1.

similar in character and occur in approximately the same wavelength range. The spectra obtained in various solvents reveal a single smooth band in the region of their longest wavelength maximum and the band changes in a fairly smooth manner with solvents, that is, there are no changes in the shape of curves. Dimethylamine salt shows an additional low intensity peak at 226 nm in ethanol, which seems to be due to general absorption of the

saturated molecule. The intensities of the n→π* bands are also considerably influenced by the solvent and specially the integrated intensity in water is much large than in any other solvent (Tables 1-4).

The transition energies of these amino-derivatives of d-camphor-β-sulphonic acid in various solvents are plotted against Z-values (Figs. 1-7). A moderately good linear relationship has been observed between

the band position (as transition energies) and the Z-values for solvents. In the case of methylamine, ethylamine, and n-propylamine salts, linearity is strikingly good (with an average deviation of ± 0.15 kcal mol⁻¹ of the points from the straight line). This linear relationship may be taken as a support for the electrical parallelism between the n $\rightarrow$ π^* transition and the charge transfer transition which defines the Z-value. Furthermore, it may be concluded that the derivatives are rigid cyclic carbonyl compounds^{8,9}.

The amino salts of d-camphor- β -sulphonic acid in the nonhydroxyl solvent pyridine, show marked differences between the calculated and actual values of transition energies, and thus are indicative of specific solute-solvent interactions. The transition in pyridine requires less energy than predicted from plots of E_T vs Z (2.42, 2.0308 and 2.0 kcal mol⁻¹, in ethylamine, isopropylamine and dimethylamine salts, respectively). The nitrogen atom in pyridine may act as donor and may form charge transfer complexes with these derivatives, resulting in the lowering of the transition energy.

A low value of transition energy in acetonitrile compared to DMF and DMSO may be attributed to less effective hydrogen bonding than either in DMF or DMSO. The stronger the hydrogen bond in n $\rightarrow$ π^* transition, the higher is the transition energy¹⁰. In the case of hydroxylic solvents, blue shifts are found to decrease in the order, H₂O > CH₃OH > C₂H₅OH > i-C₃H₇OH. This effect of hydroxylic solvents is attributed, at least partly, to the hydrogen-bonding between solute and solvent molecules. The carbonyl oxygen in Reichler's acid derivatives with lone pair of electrons acts as electron donor to the hydrogen of the hydroxyl group of the solvent molecule. Thus, it is evident that the extent of solute-solvent hydrogen bonding is apparently dependent on the acidity of alcohol. A similar trend has been found by Chandra and Basu¹¹.

Brealy and Kasha¹⁰ pointed out that hydrogen bonding lowers the energy of n-orbital by an amount approximately equal to the energy of hydrogen bond. But Pimentel¹² has shown, in his analysis of solvent effects, that the magnitude of blue shift of the n $\rightarrow$ π^* transition is not a direct measure of the energy of hydrogen-bonding between solute and solvent. Kosower⁸ developed a simple model of the transitions which permits an estimate of the hydrogen bonding energy from uv spectral data. If we consider the excited state of n $\rightarrow$ π^* transition as represented by the structure I, and make the simplifying assumption that the polarization already present in the ground state II, is unaffected by the excitation, the resultant dipole moment for the excited state will be very close to zero. This will then be analogous to that of the l-alkylpyridinium iodide complexes in which the destabilization of the excited state upon transfer of the complex dipole from one solvent to another was equal to the stabilization of the ground state⁸. The hydrogen bonding energy is estimated as half of the change in transition energy from the gas phase or more simply from

a non-polar solvent (dioxane in our case) to the polar solvent.

The hydrogen bonding or, more simply, interaction energies based on the above model have been calculated for the following compounds in water: methylamine salt (0.866), ethylamine salt (0.866), dimethylamine salt (0.866), isopropylamine salt (1.034) and ethanolamine salt (0.949), with the values of energy (kcal mol⁻¹) in parentheses.

The solvent sensitivity of the n $\rightarrow$ π^* transition, which is a measure of the degree to which the position of the n $\rightarrow$ π^* transition responds to the polarity of the solvent, can be obtained as an experimental measure, as the difference between transition energies, $E_T(\text{water}) - E_T(\text{chloroform})$ ¹³. The solvent sensitivity can also be evaluated from the product of a slope 'm' (of the least square line drawn to relate points in Figures, with respect to Z, i.e. $m = dE_T/dZ$), and ΔZ , which is the difference in the Z-values of water and chloroform. The solvent sensitivities of the isopropylamine salt and dimethylamine salt are slightly higher than the other salts (Table 5). The other salts show small variations in

TABLE 5-- SOLVENT SENSITIVITIES OF AMINO SALTS OF d-CAMPHOR- β -SULPHONIC ACID

Compound	n $\rightarrow$ π^* Transition]		
	E_T † kcal mol ⁻¹	m	m ΔZ * kcal mol ⁻¹
Ammonium salt	1.740	0.121	2.214
Methylamine salt	1.740	0.064	2.010
Ethylamine salt	1.740	0.066	2.072
n-Propylamine salt	1.740	0.067	2.104
Isopropylamine salt	2.070	0.083	2.597
Dimethylamine salt	2.070	0.076	2.870
Ethanolamine salt	1.900	0.066	2.070

† Defined as difference between water and chloroform transition energies.

* Numbers of this column should be compared with those under ΔE_T .

the overall solvent sensitivity which decreases in the order, ammonium > ethanolamine > n-propylamine > ethylamine > methylamine salts.

The above order of solvent sensitivities reveals that as the inductive nature (+I) of the side chain increases the solvent sensitivity increases. The ammonium salt is anomalous. A possible explanation for the decrease in solvent sensitivities may be given on the basis of intra-molecular hydrogen bonding between the ketonic group and hydrogen atoms attached to nitrogen (structure III). The replacement of a methyl group by an ethyl group must weaken intra-molecular hydrogen bonding and thus permit a somewhat more highly organized cybotactic region in ethylamine salt. In isopropylamine and dimethylamine salts the greater solvent sensitivity can also be attributed to the same-reason,

as in these cases the electron density on the nitrogen atom will be more than in other salts, thus making

in the ammonium salt, resulting in the higher solvent sensitivity.

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the intra-molecular hydrogen bonding even more difficult Yoshida *et al.*¹⁴ have also shown in the case of anthraquinones, that 1-aminoanthraquinone forms stronger inter- as well as intra-molecular hydrogen bonding than 1-methylamine and 1-dimethylamine anthraquinone. These Reichler's acid derivatives are capable of forming intra- as well as inter-molecular hydrogen bondings. The inter-molecular hydrogen bonding will be most favoured

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